

Why, AI.

BUSTED

MYTH

A photograph of several icebergs floating in a dark blue ocean under a grey, overcast sky. The icebergs are white and jagged, with some smaller pieces of ice visible in the foreground. The overall mood is somber and desolate.

AI will save us from climate change!

MYTH

LET'S TALK ABOUT CLIMATE CHANGE

How to address Climate Change

Mitigation: Reducing greenhouse gas emissions

Adaptation: Resilience to consequences of climate change

World Greenhouse Gas Emissions in 2016

Total: 49.4 GtCO₂e

Source: Greenhouse gas emissions on Climate Watch. Available at: <https://www.climatewatchdata.org>

TACKLING CLIMATE CHANGE WITH AI

Electricity systems

Buildings & cities

Transportation

Farms & forests

Climate prediction

Industry

Societal adaptation

Electricity Systems

Forecast Solar and Wind Generation

Electricity Systems

Identifying Rooftop Solar PV

DeepSolar from Yu et al. (2019)

Electricity Systems

Predictive maintenance:

Power line inspection (Nguyen et al. 2018)

Electricity Systems

Flexibility

Buildings as energy storage (Voss et al. 2021)

Climate impacts: Integrated Assessment Models for assess Financial Climate Risk and calculate Social cost of carbon

Financial climate risk

Social cost of carbon

Image sources:

<https://climateactiontracker.org/global/temperatures/>
<https://cicero.oslo.no/en/CF-transitional-risk>

Financial climate risk prediction

Individual banks' value at risk under green and brown investment strategies (Battiston et al. 2017)

Global climate-induced sovereign ratings changes (2100, RP 8.5) (Klusak et al. 2021)

Social cost of carbon

Modeling the influence of the climate on social outcomes (Carleton & Hsiang 2016)

CCAI webinar with Tamma Carleton on the Social Cost of Carbon : https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_9oWvXg3dzw

Components of improved models to estimate the social cost of carbon (Carleton & Greenstone 2021)

Text as data for climate policy

PARIS AGREEMENT

The Parties to this Agreement,

Being Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, hereinafter referred to as "the Convention",

Pursuant to the Durban Platform for Enhanced Action established by decision 1/CP.17 of the Conference of the Parties to the Convention at its seventeenth session,

In pursuit of the objective of the Convention, and being guided by its principles, including the principle of equity and common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities, in the light of different national circumstances,

- (a) Holding the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels, recognizing that this would significantly reduce the risks and impacts of climate change;
- (b) Increasing the ability to adapt to the adverse impacts of climate change and foster climate resilience and low greenhouse gas emissions development, in a manner that does not threaten food production; and
- (c) Making finance flows consistent with a pathway towards low greenhouse gas emissions and climate-resilient development.

Per-document, per topic probabilities for groups of climate actors based on topic modelling approach (Hsu & Rauber 2021)

A large iceberg floats in the dark blue ocean under a dark sky. The iceberg is white and jagged, with a smaller piece of ice visible in the distance to the left.

***AI alone* will not save us from climate change!**

BUSTED
MYTH

AI also has the potential to harm the climate

Direct impact

GHG emissions from computational requirements (Strubell et al. 2019)

Indirect impact

AI applications in areas that have a negative impact on the climate

AI is one piece of the puzzle

ML is a powerful tool
... but not a silver bullet.

Where ML is relevant, **collaboration** is key to doing meaningful work.

Climate Change AI

Catalyzing impactful work at the intersection of climate change and AI

Digital resources

Foundational report, datasets and add'l resources

Resource Wiki & meetups

Electricity Systems

+ Forecasting supply and demand

High Leverage

+ Improving scheduling and flexible demand

Conferences and events

Workshops at major machine learning conferences ICML, NeurIPS and ICLR.

Funding programs

Global research funding to be announced for impactful work in climate change + AI

INNOVATION RESEARCH NETWORK IN AFRICA

Newsletter and forum

Climate Change AI Newsletter

In this edition of the Climate Change AI newsletter, we're excited to share opportunities to engage with the wider community, across domains and around the world. Read on to discover meetings, articles, podcasts, and more.

Do you have opportunities to share or other content you would like to see included in the newsletter? Get in touch at info@climatechange.ai. For discussion with fellow readers, follow [@ClimateChangeAI](https://twitter.com/ClimateChangeAI) on twitter or join our forum.

News

Calls for Submissions

Funding

Projects & Courses

Readings

Jobs

Webinars and happy hours

Spatial planning of low-carbon cities with machine learning

Cities represent the lion's share of the world's energy use and GHG emissions, requiring rapid mitigation action. The spatial configurations of the built environment, in particular buildings and streets, strongly impact energy requirements for housing and mobility, depending for example on the density or destination accessibility in cities. In this webinar, we will go over machine learning approaches to analyze large volumes of data and find urban planning strategies that can both reduce the carbon footprint of cities and improve the quality of life of their residents.

Friday, June 18, 2021

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Learn more:

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 [@ClimateChangeAI](https://twitter.com/ClimateChangeAI)

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